

Transient Hypopituitarism in a Patient Developing Diabetic Ketoacidosis after COVID-19: Case Report

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Abstract: Since the beginning of the novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic, many papers have been published about the association between COVID-19 and various endocrine abnormalities. Accumulated data so far reveal that hyperglycemic conditions such as the deterioration of glycemic control and ketoacidosis in diabetic people, and new-onset diabetes mellitus become prominent as the mainly endocrine manifestations of this disease. However, it has not yet been clearly described the potential negative impacts of COVID-19 on the pituitary gland. Herein we present a 41-year-old man with diabetes mellitus that diabetic ketoacidosis and transient hypopituitarism developed simultaneously following COVID-19. We aimed to emphasize via this report that COVID-19 may be associated with not only hyperglycemia but also pituitary dysfunction, even such endocrine complications may also occur in the same patient as in our case.

Keywords: Case report; Hypopituitarism; Central hypothyroidism; Diabetic ketoacidosis; COVID-19.

Introduction

COVID-19 is an infectious disease caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) that leads to the death of millions of people since it was first identified in December 2019. Although SARS-CoV-2 mainly involves the upper respiratory tract, fatal complications including pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome may occur in some patients. Furthermore, various extra-pulmonary manifestations, some of them affecting the endocrine glands, have also been described in the course of COVID-19 pandemic. However, few cases of hypopituitarism associated with COVID-19 have been reported^[1-3]. It is a known phenomenon that hypopituitarism may accompany various viral infections such as hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome (HFRS) which is caused by Hantaviruses^[4]. Moreover, a series of cases with transient hypothalamic-pituitary dysfunction associated with SARS-CoV has also been reported following the previous SARS pandemic which outbreaks in 2003^[5].

Diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA), an acute metabolic complication of diabetes mellitus, is characterised with hyperglycemia and lipolysis caused by absolute lack of insulin. Although the most common cause of DKA is omission of insulin treatment in the patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus, it may also be precipitated by many infections including also COVID-19 in both type 1 and type 2 diabetics. On the other hand, the clinic view of sudden-onset hypopituitarism as in the case of pituitary apoplexy may be

confused with DKA because of the similarity of their common symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, weakness, headache, visual impairment, and altered mental status. Notwithstanding, the coexistence of these two distinct clinic entities is extremely rare. To the best of our knowledge, this case is the first patient who has been reported to have transient hypopituitarism concurrently with DKA following COVID-19.

Case Report

A 41-year-old male patient had been admitted to the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) of Gozde Academy Hospital with complaints of the breakdown of general condition, shortness of breath, and loss of consciousness. The progressive worsening of the patient's health situation in recent days was stated by his relatives. Our patient had undergone COVID-19 pneumonia two weeks ago, however, he had improved both clinically and radiologically as well as the real-time reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction test had turned negative during this period. The patient who was diagnosed with diabetes mellitus 15 years ago was being treated with oral antidiabetic agents (metformin and gliclazide). Nevertheless, his antidiabetic medications had been changed (vildagliptin instead of gliclazide and a combination of empagliflozin/metformin instead of metformin, respectively) shortly before COVID-19 pneumonia. On the other hand, he had been treated with insulin only during COVID-19 pneumonia, then had continued taking his orally antidiabetic drugs in the time between pneumonia and ketoacidosis.

At the admission to the ICU, the patient's general condition was poor. The patient who was able to open his eyes in response to pain and also localize the painful stimuli could not respond to verbal commands (Glasgow Coma Scale was E2M5V1). Vital signs of the patient, whose pupils were isochoric and mid-dilated

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as well as reactive to light, were as follows; oxygen saturation by pulse oximetry 85% on room air, body temperature 36.9 °C, blood pressure 88/66 mmHg, and heart rate 118 beats/min. On physical examination, his skin was pale and cold, moreover, he was breathing deeply and rapidly (Kussmaul breathing pattern).

In addition to oxygen therapy via nasal cannula, intravenous insulin and isotonic fluid treatment under close monitoring was started to the patient who was diagnosed DKA by arterial blood gas and urine analyses following the first evaluation (arterial blood gas parameters have been shown in Table 1). As soon as the severity of ketoacidosis was comprehended, sodium bicarbonate infusion was also given. Moreover, piperacillin/tazobactam (18 g/day) and methylprednisolone (40 mg/day) were empirically added to the treatment taking into account the possibility of sepsis and critical illness-related corticosteroid insufficiency (CIRCI). On the other hand, central hypothyroidism was noticed on initial laboratory examination. Thereupon, hormone tests were performed to include other anterior pituitary hormones except those adrenocorticotropic hormone (ACTH), growth hormone (GH), and insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) which could not be analyzed because of technical inability, and finally hypopituitarism was revealed. The test results were confirmed by repeated analysis, however, any pituitary lesion was not able to be detected on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the sellar region. Laboratory data including also an overt hypopituitarism at the acceptance to the ICU have been summarized in Table 2.

Table 1. Arterial Blood Gas Analysis Pointing to Severe Ketoacidosis.

Test	Result	Reference Range
pH	6.989	7.35 – 7.45
SaO ₂	83.5%	95 – 100
PaO ₂	61.4 mmHg	80 – 100
PaCO ₂	21.1 mmHg	35 – 45
Bicarbonate	4.8 mmol/L	22 – 26
Anion gap	-24.3 mmol/L	3 – 10

pH: Potential of Hydrogen, SaO₂: Saturation of Oxygen, PaO₂: Partial Pressure of Oxygen, PaCO₂: Partial Pressure of Carbon Dioxide.

Contrary to the loss of anterior pituitary hormones, the posterior pituitary was intact. The patient did not have any symptom suggesting diabetes insipidus such as polyuria and polydipsia as well as both his fluid balance and density of urine were normal along clinical follow-up. After the resolution of ketoacidosis by intravenous fluid and insulin infusion, it was switched to intensive insulin therapy. Furthermore, low dose levothyroxine (25 microgram per day) was started to treat central hypothyroidism. Eventually, the patient whose dose of corticosteroid was gradually reduced was discharged on the 7th day of the treatment in consequence of the improvement of his clinical condition.

When the patient applied to the outpatient clinic seven days after discharge, both levothyroxine and methylprednisolone treatments were discontinued. On repeated measurement, the serum concentration of c-peptide was 3.85 ng/mL (normal ranges; 0.9 – 4). Since the patient's endogenous insulin reserve was sufficient, antidiabetic treatment with oral antidiabetic agents (metformin

and nateglinide) was continued in addition to basal insulin glargine instead of intensive treatment. Finally, our patient was re-evaluated in terms of the pituitary functions two weeks after the discontinuation of levothyroxine and methylprednisolone treatments. As a result, it was detected that all the lost pituitary hormones returned to their normal levels, as seen in Table 3.

Table 2. Initial Laboratory Results of the Patient.

Test	Result	Reference Range
Hb	16 g/dL	14 – 18
Hct	46.8%	40 – 52
Plt	302x10 ³ /mL	150 – 400
WBC	26.2x10 ³ /mL	3.8 – 10
Neutrophil counts	22.4x10 ³ /mL	2 – 8
NLR	18.66	0.78 – 3.53
CRP	17.09 mg/L	0 – 5
Procalcitonin	0.13 ng/mL	0 – 0.1
Glucose	222 mg/dL	70 – 110
Urea	81 mg/dL	10 – 50
Creatinine	1.61 mg/dL	0.3 – 1.4
Uric Acid	9.1 mg/dL	3.4 – 4.7
AST	27 IU/L	8 – 45
ALT	45 IU/L	8 – 45
Total Protein	6.17 g/dL	6 – 8.3
Albumine	3.3 g/dL	3.5 – 5.0
Sodium	141 mmol/L	136 – 145
Potassium	4.42 mmol/L	3.5 – 5.1
Calcium (corrected)	7.99 mg/dL	8.4 – 10.2
Phosphorus	2.34 mg/dL	2.5 – 5.1
HbA1c	7.6%	4.1 – 5.7
C-peptide	1.4 ng/mL	0.9 – 4
TSH	0.58 µIU/mL	0.27 – 4.5
Free T3 (double-checked)	0.75 pg/mL	2.1 – 4.25
Free T4 (double-checked)	0.6 ng/dL	0.93 – 1.71
FSH (double-checked)	0.8 mIU/mL	1.4 – 18.1
LH (double-checked)	0.87 mIU/mL	1.5 – 9.3
Testosterone (double-checked)	2.44 ng/mL	2.8 – 8
Prolactin	8.35 ng/mL	0 – 20
Cortisol	4.63 µg/dL	6.02 – 18.4

Hb: Hemoglobin, Hct: Hematocrit, Plt: Platelet, WBC: White Blood Cell, NLR: Neutrophil-to-Lymphocit Ratio, CRP: C-Reactive Protein, AST: Aspartate Aminotransferase, ALT: Alanine Aminotransferase, HbA1c: Glycosylated Hemoglobin, TSH: Thyroid Stimulating Hormone, T3: Triiodothyronine, T4:

Thyroxine, FSH: Follicle-Stimulating Hormone, LH: Luteinizing Hormone.

Table 3. Spontaneous Normalization in Hormone Levels During Follow-up.

Test	Result	Reference Range
TSH	1.38 μ U/mL	0.27 – 4.5
Free T3	3.08 pg/mL	2.1 – 4.25
Free T4	1.28 ng/dL	0.93 – 1.71
FSH	1.96 mIU/mL	1.4 – 18.1
LH	4.89 mIU/mL	1.5 – 9.3
Testosterone	5.2 ng/mL	2.8 – 8
Cortisol	14.98 μ g/dL	6.02 – 18.4

The abbreviations have been shown on Table 2.

Discussion

It is known that the coronavirus enters into host cells via the angiotensin converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor, moreover, ACE2 mRNA expression has been demonstrated in many tissues, including the hypothalamus and the pituitary gland^[6]. Additionally, after the coronavirus invades the nasopharyngeal epithelium, it can reach the brain through the olfactory nerve and cause some common symptoms such as anosmia, hyposmia, headache, and confusion^[7]. Based on this information, it may be hypothesized that SARS-CoV-2 can potentially affect hypothalamo-pituitary functions by either transmission via the olfactory nerve or direct extension from the sphenoid sinuses. On the other hand, transient hypopituitarism has also been identified in the convalescent phase of some viral infections, mainly Puumala virus that is a member of the *Hantavirus* genus. These viruses lead to HFRS which is characterized with vascular leakage, circulatory collapse with hypotension, shock, and acute renal failure. Although the exact cause of hypopituitarism developing after such viral infections is not known, autoimmunity and hypothalamic-pituitary ischemia due to the vascular damage have been suggested as the possible mechanisms^[4,8]. Similarly, central hypocortisolism emerging 1 week after the recovery has been shown in a patient with COVID-19 without any pituitary lesion^[9]. In addition, a case of hypopituitarism due to hypophysitis has also been recently reported following mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 vaccination^[10]. In our case, the unexpected encounter with central hypothyroidism in the first laboratory examination was a clue for the diagnosis of hypopituitarism. If hypopituitarism had been overlooked, the prognosis might have been worse. Therefore, we consider that methylprednisolone therapy initiated before the diagnosis of hypopituitarism to be protected from possible CIRCI may have prevented a catastrophic outcome.

Similar to Enteroviruses involved in the etiology of type 1 diabetes, SARS-Cov-2 can also target pancreatic islet cells and lead to transient hyperglycemia and ketoacidosis resulting from autoimmune damage of insulin-producing β -cells. As a matter of fact, although the c-peptide level of our patient increased after DKA, it was close to the lower limit during ketoacidosis. Nevertheless, we consider that the addition of empagliflozin to antidiabetic therapy before COVID-19 pneumonia was remarkable. Empagliflozin, an inhibitor of sodium-glucose co-transporter-2

(SGLT2), is an oral glucose-lowering agent acting by inhibition of glucose reabsorption in the proximal renal tubules. Meta-analyses of some randomized controlled trials and many systematic reviews have revealed that SGLT2 inhibitors may increase the risk of DKA in patients with diabetes^[11,12]. Our patient had recently had COVID-19 pneumonia as a risk factor predisposing to the development of DKA. Nevertheless, another point to be noted in our case is that empagliflozin might also have created a susceptibility to ketoacidosis.

Despite a few reported cases, the coexistence of hypopituitarism and DKA is exceptional, especially in the absence of a previously known pituitary lesion. In some of these cases, there were plausible reasons to occur this combination, such as hypopituitarism caused by pituitary abscess in a patient with DKA^[13] and a newly diagnosed ketosis-prone type 2 diabetes due to overtreatment with glucocorticoids in a patient with Sheehan's syndrome^[14]. However, a clear causal association could not be determined in the remaining cases. On the other hand, it has been reported that pituitary apoplexy can be triggered by DKA even without a pituitary mass^[15,16]. Various hypotheses, such as cerebral edema and ischemia that may accompany ketoacidosis, have been proposed to explain this rare clinical entity^[17].

COVID-19 may be separately associated with DKA and hypopituitarism via different pathophysiological mechanisms as mentioned above. In our case, functional hypopituitarism was probably an unusual manifestation of COVID-19 because no pituitary lesion was seen on MRI of the sella, and the hypopituitarism resolved spontaneously within a few weeks. Nevertheless, the simultaneous occurrence of DKA and hypopituitarism may be merely a coincidence. In any case, this rare clinical entity seems remarkable to us. Since ACTH, GH and IGF-1 could not be measured, we could not determine whether there was a loss of all anterior pituitary hormones. Therefore, we accept this technical inability as a limitation of our study. However, in our case, both central hypothyroidism and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism were evident. Despite all this, it is clear that more observations are essential on the possible connection between COVID-19 and transient hypopituitarism.

As a conclusion, the extrapulmonary involvement of COVID-19 has gained more attention with increasing the number of infected people worldwide. Therefore, we report this rare coexistence to raise awareness about some endocrinological complications of COVID-19. Additionally, we recommend that symptoms such as weakness, fatigue and loss of libido should be carefully monitored following COVID-19 and be taken into account the possibility of hypopituitarism if these symptoms persist. Further knowledge on possible mechanisms of interaction between COVID-19 and the endocrine system may contribute to the development of new follow-up strategies and therapeutic approaches.

Abbreviations

ACE2, angiotensin converting enzyme 2; ACTH, adrenocorticotropic hormone; CIRCI, critical illness-related corticosteroid insufficiency; COVID, coronavirus disease; DKA, diabetic ketoacidosis; GH, growth hormone; HFRS, hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome; ICU, intensive care unit; IGF-1, insulin-like growth factor-1; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging; mRNA,

messenger ribonucleic acid; SARS-CoV, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus; SARS-CoV-2, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2; SGLT2, sodium-glucose co-transporter-2.

Conflicts of interest

All authors declared that there are no conflicts of interest.

Authors' contributions

AG and SF contributed to this study equally. All authors read and approved the final version.

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